

CHARACTERISTIC OF USING PORTFOLIO IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES

Kalandarova Safiya Tokhirovna

Phd The Academy of Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Docent of department of "Languages" Doctoral student of Jizzakh state
pedagogical University
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Abstract

This paper presents the methods, forms and techniques of working with the language portfolio in high education system, which can be used by teachers to increase the motivation of students to learn a foreign language.

Key words: language portfolio, high education systems, assessment, evaluation, skill, motivation, development

Аннотация

В данной работе представлены методы, формы и приемы работы с языковым портфолио в системе высшего образования, которые могут быть использованы преподавателями для повышения мотивации студентов к изучению иностранного языка.

Ключевые слова: языковой портфель, высшее учебное заведение, оценивание, навык, мотивация, развития

Аннотация

Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim tizimida til portfeli bilan ishlashning metodlari, shakllari va usullari keltirilgan bo'lib, o'qituvchilar tomonidan talabalarning chet tilini o'rganishga bo'lgan motivatsiyasini oshirishda foydalanish mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: til portfeliyasi, boshlang'ich va o'rta maktab, baholash, baholash, malaka, motivasiya, rivojlanish

Introduction. As part of the implementation of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan 1875 "On measures to further improve foreign language learning system" and the National Program for Personnel Training, a comprehensive system of teaching foreign languages has been created in the country, aimed at creating a harmoniously developed, highly educated, modern-minded young generation, and further integration of the republic into the world community. Since modern education sets new goals for us, namely: to create conditions that ensure the development of individual abilities of each student, the development and education of the ability and readiness for independent and continuous study of a foreign language, further self-education with its help, the use of a foreign language in other areas of knowledge. In this regard, the role of the modern

teacher is changing. The teacher of the high education systems seems to us to be a mentor who should help the students see and realize his uniqueness, help him to study himself. The mentor is designed to help the students make the right choice, must teach the student to set goals, predict the outcome and be able to plan his educational process expediently. It is necessary to teach the student to learn so that he continues to continuously develop without a teacher. When using a foreign language in the learning process, the position and role of the teacher noticeably changes. Now the teacher is primarily the organizer, the adviser. The main purpose of the teacher is to build a subject-subject relationship, create a favorable educational environment that can provide students with the opportunity to choose methods of work, ensure the independence of students in decision-making and their responsibility for their choice, an environment that will stimulate self-knowledge and self-determination of students. The technology of the language portfolio is a technology of personality-oriented learning aimed at developing students' skills in reflecting on the process and the results of their own academic work.

Materials. First of all, we will talk about how to make technology of the language portfolio. Portfolio is one of the most promising technologies for teaching foreign languages, which, in addition to increasing the motivation for independent educational activities, allows students to become aware of the responsibility for their formation as a person, and helps each student. This promising learning tool is characterized by methodologists as an alternative form of control, which allows to obtain a dynamic picture of the educational and language development of students, as one of the possible ways to implement systematic self-control and integrate it in the process of teaching the English language. The language portfolio is the basis of increasing the motivation for independent student activity in the study of a foreign language in order to further ensure the continuity of language self-education throughout life.

Discussion. The language portfolio is: "A package of working materials that represent a particular result of a student's learning activities in mastering a foreign language. Such a package of materials gives the student and teacher the opportunity to independently and jointly analyze and evaluate the student's workload and range of achievements in the field of language and culture learning, the dynamics of mastering the language studied in various aspects, as well as the experience of educational activity in this area. "A method of fixing, accumulating and evaluating the individual achievements of the student in a certain period of his education.

"It is an instrument of self-esteem and the student's own cognitively creative work, reflection of his own activity. The first attempts at a theoretical justification for using a portfolio to change the student's knowledge assessment system were made in the USA in the early 80s. At the initial stage, the portfolio strategy implied only a focused collection of diverse student work that would allow the teacher to gradually monitor the student's educational and production activities based on analysis of samples and products of his labor. From the very beginning, the portfolio was considered as an open system, which makes it possible to constantly update by changing the content of the headings, replacing the work with

more successful and high-quality ones as the student's knowledge and skills increase when studying a specific topic module or after a certain period of time. Further development of the portfolio system revealed its new capabilities. So in 1997, T. M. Cuse, a professor at the University of South Carolina, published the book "Measure for Measure," which provides an indepth analysis of the portfolio's many-sided capabilities in mathematics and student knowledge. The book was the result of an analysis of many years of practical work on portfolio research. Experience has allowed the author to talk about different types of portfolios depending on their focus. In 1998-2000, the Language Policy Division at the Council of Europe in Strasbourg developed and piloted the European Language Portfolio as a tool to support the development of multiculturalism and multilingualism. The European Language Portfolio is based on the document "Common European Framework of Reference", which was adopted by the Council of Europe in 1996 in Strasbourg. Its purpose is to describe the levels of proficiency in a particular language in accordance with existing international standards and to facilitate the comparison of different qualification systems. The main goal of the portfolio is to develop students' self-esteem skill when working with the level scale.

Portfolio allows you to:

- maintain a high educational motivation of students;
- strengthen the situation of success in educational activities, which contributes to the positive self-assertion of the individual, affects the formation of value attitudes;
- encourage their activity and independence,
- expand the possibilities of learning and self-learning;

- develop the skills of reflective and evaluative (self-evaluating) student activities;
- to form the ability to learn - to set goals, plan and organize your own educational activities;
- To promote the individualization of education of students;
- lay additional prerequisites and opportunities for successful socialization;
- the student to keep a record of their language learning and independently assess their level using tables, set individual goals;
- create conditions for the manifestation of the student's creativity and his creative self-realization in the language, information and educational environment;
- to provide continuous study of language and culture in the context of variable language education.

The systematic gradual filling of the language portfolio implements the idea of lifelong education and acquires special significance when the student moves from one level of instruction to another.

Language portfolio increases the motivation of students, their responsibility for the results of the educational process, promotes the development of a conscious attitude of students to the learning process and its results. The language portfolio allows you to specify the goals of teaching foreign languages and, therefore, it is better to organize the learning process, teaches you to analyze the learning process together with students, based on the student's self-esteem, his needs and motivations, adjust the content of training, and find an individual approach to students.

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